

I-GEOARCHive Data Management Plan

1 Data collection and documentation

1.1 What data will be collected and generated?

The research will generate images (.tiff/.jpeg) and database entries (descriptions, keywords, images) resulting from microscopic analysis. The data are generated from:

- Reports, published and unpublished manuscripts and specialist reports from archaeological excavations
- Microscopic analysis of thin sections; descriptions of polished sections of impregnated block samples

1.2 How will the data be collected and generated?

The data is generated for each archaeological site following the archaeological layer documentations of selected profiles. The basic unit is the “Micromorphological Unit”, which can be an archaeological layer or a subdivided archaeological layer.

The Micromorphology data registering will be done by the use of an optical microscope (in plain and polarized light). Data can be recorded within I-GEOARCHrec (FileMaker database), or directly within the online database I-GEOARCHive. The data collection follows international standards for micromorphology after:

1. Bullock, P., Fedoroff, N., Jongerius, A., Stoops, G., Tursina, T. (1985). Handbook for Soil Thin Section Description. Waine Research Publications, Wolverhampton.
2. Stoops, G. (2003). Guidelines for Analysis and Description of Soil and Regolith Thin Sections. Soil Science Society of America Inc., Madison, Wisconsin.
3. Stoops, G., Marcelino, V., Mees, F. (2018). Interpretation of micromorphological features of soils and regoliths. Elsevier, Amsterdam

The control of the consistency and quality of the collected data as well as the use of a defined vocabulary will be regularly checked by the project leaders of I-GEOARCHive.

1.3 What documentation will you provide with the data?

README files will be prepared for the content and the utilisation of the database I-GEOARCHive. This will contain all the necessary information on the data structure, data recording using keywords and labelling of the files. The metadata are published on <https://www.dasch.swiss/>.

2. Copyright and Intellectual Property Rights

Our data will be made available for the public after FAIR and EOSC Data Principles. If appropriate credit is given, our data can be used for non-commercial purposes (creative commons: CC BY-NC-SA 4.0; <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/>). Third-party data will be used if it is published and freely available, if not, permission will be asked beforehand.

3 Data storage and preservation

Data storage is provided by DaSCH (Swiss National Data and Service Centre for the Humanities) (<https://www.dasch.swiss/>). Data from I-GEOARCHrec are regularly integrated into I-GEOARCHive.